

ECO-FLEX PAVEMENT: SUSTAINABLE FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT DESIGN USING WASTE PLASTIC AND RECYCLED CONCRETE AGGREGATE

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Abstract - In this study, the use of waste plastic and recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) as cutting-edge, sustainable materials for road pavement construction is investigated. The purpose of the study is to assess waste plastic bonded with aggregate to be used in the surface course and RCA performance in the GSB (Granular Subbase) layer of flexible pavement for the building of sustainable road infrastructure. The waste plastic is broken up into small pieces, coated in aggregate, combined with heated bitumen, and utilized to create a mixture that is used in the surface course. The analysis is carried out on the plastics used from PET bottles that are considered waste after their use. Bitumen is replaced with plastic at percentages of 3%, 5%, 10%, and 15%. The present study also investigates the results obtained by partially replacing the natural aggregates of the GSB (Granular Subbase) layer of traditional flexible pavement with recycled concrete aggregates by comparing the results of proctor test and CBR values with the specifications and guidelines provided by the Ministry of Road Transport and Highways, Government of India. The physical and mechanical properties of recycled concrete aggregate are almost similar when compared to natural aggregate. The combination of plastic-modified bitumen and recycled aggregates in flexible pavements represents a significant step towards creating more sustainable and resilient road infrastructure.

Key Words: Flexible Pavement, Plastic waste, Recycled material, Sustainability, Environment friendly, Durability, Strength, Reduced thickness, Cost effective.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global infrastructure industry has been dealing with two major issues in recent years: effectively managing plastic waste and sustainably using construction materials. Innovative methods are being investigated to incorporate waste materials into construction processes in order to address these challenges, with the goal of improving infrastructure performance while also protecting the environment. This project centers on using waste plastic and recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) in the construction of flexible pavements, an essential part of transportation infrastructure. Flexible pavements are created to endure the moving loads caused by vehicular traffic while offering longevity and usability throughout their lifespan.

Ahmad M. Abu Abdo and S. J. Jung, (2019) have mentioned that officials in Ras Al Khaimah (RAK), United Arab Emirates are facing a rise in solid waste. UAE are assessing alternatives for reusing these materials instead of disposing of them in landfills. Moreover, busy and slower traffic is causing premature failure of asphalt pavements in RAK paired with scorching temperatures in the summer. To help with the attempts to find a solution this research was carried out to examine the impact of including waste plastic on these issues Incorporating synthetic fibers into Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA). Experiments were carried out on a typical HMA using two different grades of asphalt binder and two levels of waste plastic fiber content (0.5 and 1% of mix weight). The findings indicated that the resistance of HMA to fracture at temperatures of -10 and 21.1°C, as well as rutting, was observed. The addition of waste plastic fibers caused an increase in resistance at a temperature of 54.4°C. Optimizing waste plastic fibers has led to an overall enhancement in the performance of asphalt pavement. The mixture was determined to contain 0.5% of the content by weight. By incorporating waste plastic fibers into HMA, enhancement of asphalt pavements performance by improving resistance to rutting and cracking. Reusing discarded plastic waste could have a beneficial impact on the environment.

M. A. Dalhat and H. I. Al-Abdul Wahhab (2015) have been found that there has been a significant increase in waste produced by plastic bottles and similar items in the country of Saudi Arabia. The increased level of industrial activity has led to this outcome. packaging because of quick industrialization and rapid urbanization in the nation. The cost related to the handling of these solid wastes has also increased due to the growing complexity and size of the task. The impact of recycled plastic wastes (RPW) such as polypropylene, high-density polyethylene (HDPE), and low-density polyethylene (LDPE) has been studied. Research has investigated the viscoelastic properties of the asphalt binder in the area. The plastics that were recycled were achieved by tearing and crushing the RPW into a suitable size to facilitate mixing with the asphalt folder. All RPWs lead to enhanced rutting performance. The upper PG limit of RPW-modified asphalts will also be improved. In most instances, there is a minimum one-level increase for every 2% rise in RPW content. A rise of 55 has been observed. A 9% difference in resilient modulus (MR) was found between PP-, HDPE-, and LDPE-made asphalt concrete, with PP showing a 19% variation. (AC), in that

order. The relationship between the MR of the AC and the non-recoverable creep compliance (J_{nr}) is correlated. The asphalt binder was installed. The viscoelastic properties of the RPW-modified binder were determined. employed to simulate a standard pavement structure with the AASHTO mechanistic empirical pavement design guide software called ME-PDG. The anticipated issues with the simulated pavement display notable rutting and enhanced fatigue resistance for pavement made using the RPW. Polymers of the elastomeric type are needed to be added to these RPW to help them meet the elastic recovery requirement of AASHTO TP. Anzar Hamid Mir J Eng, 2015 They have mentioned that almost 5% of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is made up of toxic plastic and an important issue at present is the management of plastic waste. These pollutants are not able to be broken down by living organisms, leading to environmental contamination and sanitation issues. Experiments conducted at various institutions have shown that waste plastic can be used in the process of paving roads. Utilizing these waste materials in building roads is influenced by economic, technical, and ecological factors. In India, the author's homeland, millions of metric tons of plastic waste are generated annually as an example. If these waste materials are effectively incorporated into road building, the issues of disposal and pollution can be greatly reduced. Bitumen is utilized as a binder during the process of constructing roads. Plastic waste pieces can be added to bitumen to create a mixture suitable for a surface course of flexible pavement, with improved binding, stability, density, and water resistance.

Yash Menaria and Rupal Sankhla (2015) have stated that the utilization of plastic in flexible pavements has been a long-standing practice to enhance road stability, durability, and reduce construction costs by replacing a portion of bitumen with waste plastic. The addition of waste plastic in bitumen results in improved properties such as penetration and softening point, contributing to enhanced road durability and stability. Plastic roads can be constructed in high-temperature areas, showcasing the versatility and applicability of this technique in various environmental conditions. Plastic in bitumen helps in compensating air voids, binds with aggregate, and provides stability to the pavement structure, contributing to improved road performance. Raghvendra Bajpai et. al. (2017) The authors demonstrated that around 5% of municipal solid waste consists of various types of plastic, which may have toxic properties. Seeing used plastic bags and other types of plastic packaging scattered on roads and drains is a frequent occurrence in urban and rural areas. Because it is biodegradable, it leads to water stagnation and hygiene issues. Experiments have been conducted to see if waste plastic can be effectively reused in road construction to address this issue. Experiments conducted at various institutions have shown that incorporating waste plastic into hot aggregate will result in a thin plastic coating on the aggregate. When this plastic-coated aggregate is combined with the binder, it shows increased strength, improved water resistance, and better long-term performance. Hence, the suggestion is to utilize waste plastic for building rural roads.

S.L. Hake et. al. (2019) addressed about the global issue of waste plastic disposal, highlighting its non-biodegradability and environmental impact. It discusses the use of waste plastic in road construction to enhance mechanical properties of bituminous mixes, focusing on replacing bitumen with plastic in flexible pavements. The paper mentions the process of grinding up plastic garbage into small pieces, melting it, and coating it over hot aggregates to create polymer-coated-bitumen aggregate for road construction. Cost analysis indicates a 5.18% cost reduction in material mix using plastic blends compared to traditional bitumen, making it a cost-effective and environmentally friendly option for road construction. Prakhar Duggal et. al. 2020 highlighted that recycled low-density polyethylene plastic can enhance the durability and fatigue life of flexible pavements. Plastic heating at 165°C does not release toxic gases, but decomposition starts above 270°C. The use of waste plastic as a bitumen modifier has shown improvements in fatigue life and abrasion resistance of pavements. The optimal plastic content in the bitumen mix is found to be 5-10% by weight of bitumen.

R. Manju Anand and Sathya.S (2017) have investigated that the waste plastic, such as polyethylene, polypropylene, and polystyrene, can be shredded, coated over aggregates, and mixed with hot bitumen to create a mix that strengthens the pavement and increases its durability. The presence of plastic in bituminous mixes reduces the formation of voids and moisture absorption in the pavement, leading to a decrease in ruts and preventing pothole formation. The use of plastic waste in bituminous mixes reduces the need for bitumen by around 10%, resulting in a more sustainable and eco-friendly road construction process. José Eduardo Salcedo Fontalvo et. al. (2023) has employed the Los Angeles abrasion value and California bearing ratio (CBR) tests to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the granular sub-base (GSB) with varying percentages of recycled concrete aggregates (RCAs) blended with natural aggregate. Particle size distribution analysis of the GSB was conducted in accordance with the ASTM D6913 standard, comparing the results with established limits for the material. Compaction characteristics were assessed following the standard Proctor methodology with a compaction energy of 600 kJ/m³, testing three samples with different moisture contents. Construction, and demolition (C&D) wastes are a growing concern globally due to increased construction activities, leading to ecological issues by N. Yadav and R. Kumar (2023). Recycling C&D waste into recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) for pavement base and sub-base layers is a viable solution to address this problem. The study evaluates the application of RCA in the construction industry using microstructural characterization, laboratory testing, and economic analysis. The sub-base layer construction utilizing 50% RCA and 50% NA resulted in a 17.86% material cost decrease, demonstrating the financial advantages of adopting RCA.

In his study of Sampat Mandlik and P. L. Naktode (2023) have mentioned the use of IITPAVE software for analyzing linear elastic layered pavement systems. The software calculates stresses, strains, and deflections caused by loads on different pavement locations, aiding in designing safe and functional pavements. It suggests that reducing the thickness of pavement layers while maintaining safe strain limits is feasible, enhancing pavement design efficiency. Shrutika Ugalmugale et. al. (2021) have discussed the a partial substitute for traditional bitumen in road construction with waste plastic and rubber, as per the literature review. Various percentages of rubber and PET were added to bitumen, with the optimal content found to be 6% by weight of bitumen. The study concluded that using PET bottles was the most effective method for improving pavement stability. Over 2000 km of roads have been constructed in Bangalore using waste plastic, showing good performance.

Using waste plastic in bituminous mixtures and recycled concrete aggregate in granular subbase layers can help meet environmental and engineering needs in pavement construction. It offers a sustainable method for managing waste plastic while also improving the characteristics of the asphalt mixture. The use of plastic-modified bitumen has demonstrated enhancements in flexibility, fatigue resistance, and rutting resistance, which could possibly prolong the lifespan of flexible pavements. Furthermore, incorporating recycled concrete aggregate in the granular subbase layer helps lower the need for natural aggregates, preserving natural resources and lessening the environmental effects linked to aggregate extraction. Advanced computational tools like the IIT PAVE software are used to assess the effectiveness of the suggested road design that includes waste plastic and recycled concrete aggregate. This software assists in analyzing and designing flexible pavements by considering factors like traffic loads, material properties, and environmental conditions. The project aims to evaluate the structural integrity, durability, and sustainability of the designed pavement system through in-depth analysis.

2. MATERIAL USED

2.1. Natural Aggregate (NA)

The primary building block for a road's construction is aggregate, an inert material. Bitumen holds these naturally occurring stones together, as they have very little reactivity. Additionally, larger rocks are artificially prepared by being broken into tiny pieces. We have utilized various aggregate sizes in different ratios based on the grading needed for the flexible pavement's wearing course design.

2.2. Bitumen

Bitumen can be produced artificially through chemical processes or obtained as a by-product of crude oil distillation. They have an extremely dense structure and are made up of complex hydrocarbons. Their melting point ranges from 80 to 120 °C. To create a surface, bitumen serves as a binding agent, holding the aggregates together. Bitumen is easily utilized for road construction because of its ductility, low melting point, and binding ability. It could repel water as well. Bitumen comes in various penetration grades, such as 30/40, 60/70, and 80/100. Viscosity parameter-based classification of bitumen is an additional method. The bitumen grade we are using for our major project experiment is VG-30 having a penetration grade of 60/70.

2.3. Waste Plastic

In this project, the bituminous mixture used to create the flexible pavement incorporates waste plastic. This creative solution reduces the amount of plastic waste that ends up in landfills, recycles it, and improves the qualities of bituminous mix. The bitumen that has been treated with plastic shows better flexibility, more resistance to rutting and cracking, and may even lengthen the pavement's life. Roads, garbage trucks, landfills, composting facilities, and waste purchasers provided the waste plastic bottles and their caps, which were collected for Rs. 5–6 per kg. For the project, household plastics like used plastic bags and empty milk cartons were also gathered. The gathered plastic waste was divided into categories based on the needed thickness. Typically, the subsequent procedure uses Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) with a micron size of 30-150 microns.

2.4. Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCA)

Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCA) is a sustainable construction material produced by crushing old or demolished concrete structures. Crushed concrete from old or demolished buildings is recycled concrete aggregate, or RCA, a sustainable building material. By taking waste from landfills, this process reduces its negative environmental effects. The quality of RCA varies, but quality control is applied. It adds to strength and is useful in new concrete mixes and road construction. RCA has financial benefits in addition to environmental ones. Its performance characteristics are the subject of research to guarantee adherence to safety regulations. Respecting the rules is essential for sustainable and ethical use in a building.

2.5. Soil

A soil sample was taken from the construction site to guarantee the flexible pavement's precise design and functionality. This sample's load-bearing capacity was assessed using the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test. This test is essential because it offers important information about the stability and strength of the subgrade soil, which has a direct bearing on the overall structure of the pavement. The CBR test results will guide the design process, ensuring that the pavement is built in a way that best suits the site's unique geotechnical characteristics and maximizing its performance and longevity.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. For preparation of surface course

At higher temperatures (160°C–170°C), less micron plastic is easily mixed with bitumen. It is clean after dusting and, if necessary, washing. Plastic that had been collected was chopped as finely as possible. After passing through a 4.75 mm sieve, the plastic fragments were collected at the 2.36 mm sieve. First, the melting point of bitumen was reached, which is between 160°C and 170°C.

In pavement construction, there are basically two methods by which plastic can be added to bitumen concrete:

1. Dry mix method
2. Wet mix method

In the dry mix method, plastic is melted and combined with bitumen at a highly controlled temperature. This mixture is combined with the aggregates to prepare bitumen concrete. This method is more cost-effective since it uses less aggregate in the mix. To ensure uniformity and consistency, the dry mix preparation is carried out under carefully monitored circumstances, which may include temperatures and mixing times. The prepared specimens are loaded in the Marshall test setup as shown in below Figure 1.

Fig -1: Prepared Marshall samples and placed them in Marshall apparatus.

3.2. For Recycled concrete aggregate

The process of adding recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) to the granular subbase layer of flexible pavement starts with gathering and readying concrete waste from demolition areas, then crushing it to create RCA of appropriate dimensions. Lab tests are conducted on the RCA to evaluate its physical and mechanical features, including particle size distribution, specific gravity, water absorption, and aggregate crushing value, in addition to its strength and durability properties. A combination is formulated for the granular subbase layer by mixing RCA and natural aggregates, to find the best ratio of RCA for meeting specific performance standards. Samples of the mixed material are prepared for testing, and compaction tests are carried out to determine the ideal moisture content and highest dry density. As shown in Figure 2, the recycled aggregate is acquired for the testing purpose after being oven dried for 24 hours.

Fig -2: Acquired Recycled concrete aggregate.

3.3. Pavement design analysis using IIT Pave

Following IRC:37 requirements, a stress-strain study of the completed flexible pavement utilizing IIT PAVE software entails several crucial procedures. To ascertain the subgrade qualities, soil samples are first taken from the construction site and subjected to various tests, such as the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test. For use in the pavement layers, recycled concrete aggregate and bituminous mixtures modified by waste plastic are also made as samples. Next, in compliance with IRC:37 criteria, the pavement structure is developed with the proper layers, utilizing waste plastic in the bituminous mixtures, and recycled concrete aggregate in the granular sub foundation. Each layer's thickness, Poisson's ratio, and modulus of elasticity are calculated and entered the IIT PAVE software. Environmental factors including moisture content and temperature fluctuations, as well as traffic loading circumstances like the kind and frequency of vehicle loads, are specified. To verify compliance, the analytical findings are compared to IRC:37 requirements. If required, pavement design optimization is performed to improve durability and performance.

The number of vehicles using the road each day and the design traffic in terms of the total number of standard axles are calculated using the traffic data gathered from the traffic volume counts survey. IITPAVE software is used to assess the pavement, which is created in accordance with IRC: 37-2018 criteria.

$$N = \frac{365 \times A \times \{(1+r)^n - 1\}}{r} \times VDF \times D \tag{1}$$

The Initial Traffic in year of completion of construction of pavement is given below,

$$A = P(1 + r)^x \tag{2}$$

Where, P=Number of commercial vehicles as per last count

x = Number of years between the last count and the year of completion of construction.

N=Cumulative number of standard axles, MSA

A=Initial Traffic in year of completion of construction, CVPD

r =Growth rate in percentage

n =Design life in years (15years)

D=Lane Distribution Factor

VDF=Vehicle Damage Factor -IRC 37:2018

For design purpose, growth rate r =5% and lane distribution factor D= 0.75- IRC 37:2018

4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Tests on Natural Aggregate

Table 1 highlights the test findings for the natural aggregates used in the pavement construction, giving important information for determining their performance and acceptability.

Table -1: Tests on natural aggregate

Natural Aggregate	Plastic content (%)	Aggregate Impact Value	Aggregate Crushing Value	Los Angeles abrasion value	Water Absorption test (%)
Without Plastic	0	11.20	15.97	28.12	1.3
With Plastic	5	9.94	14.42	26.64	1.1

4.2. Tests on Bitumen

To assess the bitumen's performance and qualities, key information is provided in Table 2, which summarizes the test findings for the bitumen used in the pavement construction.

Table -2: Tests on Bitumen

Bitumen + Plastic	Plastic content (%)	Penetration value test	Ductility Test	Flash Point	Fire Point	Softening Point test
Without Plastic	0	64mm	75cm	242 °C	290 °C	75°C
With Plastic	10	56mm	65cm	270 °C	310 °C	82°C

4.3. Marshall Stability test:

The Marshall Stability of a specimen during testing is the highest load that causes failure in the specimen. Heated to a specific temperature before being positioned in a unique testing fixture, the load steadily increased at a constant rate of 5 cm per minute. During the stability test, a dial gauge is utilized to measure the vertical deformation of the specimen. The Marshall Flow value of the specimen is the deformation at the failure point measured in increments of 0.25 mm. Initially, various specimens are prepared with varying bitumen content. The specimen showing the largest Marshall stability is considered for further study with its graph between bitumen and stability value (Chart 1) and flow value (Chart 2), which are depicted below. Plastic percentages of 3, 5, 10, and 15% are included to examine how replacing plastic impacts the Marshall characteristics of the bitumen mixture. The relationship between plastic percentage and stability (Chart 3), flow value (Chart 4), air void (Chart 5), and bulk density (Chart 6) indicates how the plastic percentage in bitumen affects its properties. The evaluation indicates that the Marshall Stability test demonstrates a decrease when the plastic percentage increases to 15% in plastic replacement. The graph illustrates the variation in waste plastic percentage used as a replacement for bitumen in bitumen concrete mixes and its corresponding effects. The results for plastic substitution are depicted in these graphs.

Chart -1: Bitumen percentage vs Marshall Stability.

Chart -2: Bitumen Percentage vs Flow Value

Chart -3: Plastic Content vs Stability at 5% Bitumen content.

Chart -4: Flow value vs Plastic Content at 5% bitumen content

Chart -5: Air Void (%) vs Plastic Content

Chart -6: Bulk Density(gm/cc) vs Plastic Content

4.4. Tests on Recycled concrete aggregate

4.4.1. Standard Proctor Test

The compaction properties were assessed using the standard proctor test and three tests were conducted on samples with varying moisture levels, and the outcomes for the assessed materials are displayed in the figure. The below Table 3 shows a detailed dry density and optimum moisture content values at various partially replaced samples for GSB.

Table -3: Dry Density and OMC of blended GSB Material

Sample	Dry density (gm/cc)	Optimum moisture content (%)
40% RCA+ 60% NA	2.01	7.69
50% RCA+ 50% NA	1.94	8.1
60% RCA+ 40% NA	1.72	8.7

RCA has higher water absorption as compared to natural aggregate. The data clearly shows this pattern with the optimal moisture content increasing with increasing RCA content which can be easily demonstrated using chart 7. On the other hand, it was anticipated that the dry density of samples decreases as the content of RCA increases in comparison to natural GSB because RCA has a lower density than the natural aggregate.

Chart -7: Dry Density vs Moisture Content of blended aggregate for GSB

4.4.2. California Bearing Ratio Test (CBR) Test

Accordance with ASTM D-1883, the CBR of the materials at 56 blows per compaction layer (five layers) was used to assess their resistance. The ideal moisture content discovered in the appropriate standard proctor compaction test was used to prepare the samples. The outcomes were contrasted with the standard's minimal requirements for GSB. The penetration vs. load charts were used to calculate the CBR of the three partially replaced GSB samples. The sample containing 60% Recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) and 40% natural aggregate (NA) showed a CBR value of 35.60%, following the samples containing 50% RCA and 50% NA and 40% RCA and 60% NA showing a CBR value of 45.90 and 59.49%, respectively. Chart 8 shows the comparison between penetration vs load for various samples.

Chart -8: CBR of Blended aggregate for GSB

4.5. Tests on Soil (Subgrade)

4.5.1. Standard Proctor Test

The dry density corresponding to water content of the soil is shown in Table 4 with its graph in chart 9.

Table -4: MDD and OMC of Subgrade soil

DRY DENSITY (gm/cc)	WATER CONTENT
1.6705	8.43
1.745	10.94
1.7904	13.78
1.768	15.6
1.694	17.73

Maximum Dry Density

OMC

Chart -9: OMC and MDD of Subgrade

4.5.2. California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of Subgrade:

The CBR test determined the soil's ability to support weight and verified that the subgrade would be suitable. Refer to Table 5 and chart 10 for the CBR values and corresponding penetration-load curve of the soil.

Chart -10: CBR of Subgrade

CBR at 2.5mm = 7.58%
CBR at 5mm = 6.33%

Table -5: Maximum dry density and CBR value of Subgrade soil

Parameters	Obtained Value	Recommended Value as per IRC 37:2018
Maximum Dry Density	1.79 (gm/cc)	>1.75 (gm/cc)
CBR value	7.58	≥ 5%

4.6 Pavement analysis

Table -6: Traffic data and other parameters required for pavement design.

Section	Design Life	CBR	Initial traffic [by equation (2)]	Cumulative number of standard axles [by equation (1)]	Total Pavement thickness
UP MAINPURI-SHIKOHABAD ROAD	15 years	7.58	900CVPD	43MSA	610mm

The pavement is examined using the IITPAVE program once it has been designed in accordance with IRC guidelines to see if the thickness of each layer has been chosen to adequately support the load and strains that the pavement has developed. Table 6 shows the parameters required for the design of flexible pavement with its stress-strain analysis in Figure 3.

Maximum strain developed at the analysis points are as follows:

- a. Tensile strain at bottom of bituminous concrete layer (Surface course) = **174.5μ < 176.22μ**
- b. Compressive strain at top of sub grade layer = **295.60μ < 386.50μ**

Fig -3: Calculation of strain values in IIT Pave Software

5. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions and observations have been generated in consideration of the findings reported in this paper.

- Bitumen and aggregates are mixed with plastic to enhance the performance of the roads. The plastic coating on aggregates decreases the empty spaces and absorption of moisture. This leads to decreased grooves in the road, preventing the formation of potholes. Eco flex pavement can endure heavy traffic and is more durable than traditional flexible pavement. Using a plastic mix, the thickness of the surface course of pavement could be reduced and the bitumen content can also be lowered by 10% while enhancing the road's strength and performance. This newly developed technology is environmentally friendly.
- The utilization of 10% waste plastic in semi dense bituminous concrete mixes showed improved Marshall results, suggesting the potential recommendation for the use of waste plastic. Nevertheless, this needs to be corroborated by additional lab tests and field performance studies.
- The properties of both bitumen and aggregate increase with the addition of plastic.
- Utilizing RCA in the GSB layer promotes sustainable construction practices by recycling concrete waste and reducing the demand for natural aggregates.
- The RCA-blended GSB layer's CBR values show a respectable load-bearing capacity that is on level with traditional aggregates, suggesting that it can be used to build pavements.
- The thickness of each layer of pavement can be reduced by a certain amount in order to reduce the strain differences obtained by using two methods: one from formulas according to IRC 37:2018, where the values of maximum tensile strain and maximum compressive strain are calculated using air voids and other parameters that are mentioned above in the tables, and the other method involves the calculation of the values of tensile and compressive strain by putting the values of each layer.

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APPENDIX

The following section presents the design principles and parameters that are used for the analysis of pavement with its cross-section as shown in figure 4.

1. Design CBR of Subgrade = 7.58%
2. Design Traffic = 50 MSA
3. Bitumen used = VG-30
4. Pavement Composition

Fig -4: Cross- section of designed flexible pavement.

5. Resilient Modulus (MR) of Subgrade = $17.6 * (CBR)^{0.64}$
 $= 64.35 \text{ MPa}$

6. Resilient Modulus (MR) of Aggregate Layer (WMM + GSB) = $0.2 * h^{0.45} * MR$ of subgrade
 $= 201.155 \text{ MPa}$

7. Poisson's Ratio for subgrade, WMM, BC and DBM is taken as 0.35- IRC 37:2018

8. Single wheel load is taken as 20000 N and tyre pressure = 0.56 MPa

9. Percentage air void = 3.64 (From chart 5 corresponding to Marshall's specimen with higher stability value)

10. Points taken for stress analysis = 4.0

11. As per parameters obtained from material permissible allowable strains for designed traffic-

Tensile Strain at the bottom of bituminous concrete layer is given by Equation –

$$N_f = 0.5161 \times C \times 10^{-4} \times \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon_t} \right]^{3.89} \times \left[\frac{1}{MR_m} \right]^{0.854} \quad (\text{For 90 \% reliability})$$

$$\varepsilon_t = 176.22 \mu$$

Allowable Compressive Strain at top of sub grade –

$$N_R = 1.4100 \times 10^{-8} \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon_p} \right]^{4.5337} \quad (\text{For 90\% reliability})$$

$$\varepsilon_v = 386.50 \mu$$

where,

N_f = standard axles load that can be served by the pavement before the critical cracked area of

20% , taken as 43 MSA (from table 6).

$$C = 10^M$$

$$M = 4.84 \left(\frac{V_{be}}{V_a + V_{be}} - 0.69 \right)$$

$$M = 4.84 \left(\frac{10.76}{3.74 + 10.76} - 0.69 \right)$$

$$M = 0.2769$$

V_{be} = % volume of effective bitumen in the mix

V_a = % volume of air void in the mix

MR_m = resilient modulus of the bituminous mix used in the bottom bituminous layer taken as

3000 MPa.

N_R = standard axles load (80kN) that can be served by the pavement before the critical rut depth of 20mm occurs, taken as 43MSA (From table 6).

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